

MYOCARDITIS AND PERICARDITIS

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Abstract. Myocarditis (myo-muscle, card-heart, itis-inflammation) is myocardial inflammation not caused by any secondary infection or disease. At the same time, pericarditis (around the heart) is inflammation in the pericardium, which is the outer covering of the heart. Myocarditis or pericarditis, also known as myopericarditis, is an inflammatory disease of the myocardium or the pericardial sac. They also show myocyte necrosis, which is nonischemic. There are varieties of signs and symptoms in myocarditis and pericarditis, such as acute heart failure, dilated chronic cardiomyopathy, and possibly even death. However, it is undetected in disease and adverse drug and vaccine reactions in critical conditions.

Most MCP is due to viral causes but can also be due to microbial pathogenesis. Toxic myocarditis (reversible) occurs in the case of diphtheria, and in some cases, when autoimmune mechanisms may contribute, it can be due to infective endocarditis. Some growing organisms like, chlamydia and trypanosome infection in Chagas disease can cause chronic myocarditis.

Pericarditis causes an acute illness and complicates rheumatic renal or malignant disease. We suggest echocardiography to ensure pericardial involvement in noncardiac conditions. We can observe pericardial pain and sometimes pericardial friction, and in ECG, we can also see ST-segment elevation.

Keywords: myocarditis, pericarditis, myopericarditis, immunization.

DEFINITION

Myocarditis is a condition in which autoimmune inflammation of the heart mainly affects children and adults. The leading common cause is a viral infection. However, in etiology, we included bacterial and protozoal infections, toxins, and reactions to some drugs. Myocarditis or pericarditis is also known as myopericarditis, an inflammatory disease of the myocardium or the pericardial sac. They also show myocyte necrosis, which is nonischemic. Therefore, acute injuries here can lead to myocyte damage, which can initiate the humoral immune system. This leads to severe inflammation.

Figure 1: MYOCARDITIS

(Here, images of healthy heart and inflamed heart are shown.)

Photo source: <https://patriciabcaston.blogspot.com/2021/06/myocarditis-causes-myocarditis-causes.htm>

PERICARDITIS

Pericarditis is inflammation in the pericardial sac. This can be associated with pericardial syndromes. In this study, we noticed increased fluid accumulation within the sac, thus forming pericardial effusion. This depends on the etiology and is further divided into serous, hemorrhagic and purulent. The pericardial cavity usually contains 15-50 ml of plasma ultrafiltrate in healthy individuals. The pericardium holds the hearts; thus, it works properly. Viral infections are the cause of pericarditis, but it can also be due to bacteria and fungi. The pericardium serves multiple functions. First, it is the anchor of the heart in the thoracic cavity.

Layers of the pericardium:

Outer parietal pericardium: fibrous layer; pain-sensitive layer.

Middle pericardium space

Inner visceral pericardium: collagen and elastin layer; pain insensitive layer.

The parietal layer is well innervated by mechanoreceptors and is thus pain sensitive.

During inspiration, the intrathoracic pressure falls and is transmitted to cardiac chambers by the pericardial space. As a result, we can observe an augmentation of venous return, pericardium expansion, and accommodation of more blood into the left ventricle.

Relation between the cardiac chamber, great vessels, thoracic cavity and pericardial space:

- The pericardial sac sits within the thoracic cavity, reflecting intrathoracic pressure.
- While the cardiac chambers lie within the confines of the pericardial sac, the pulmonary vein does not.
- The pulmonary vein exists outside the pericardial sac but within the thoracic cavity, which is directly influenced by changes in intrathoracic pressure.
- The SVC is extrapericardial and extrathoracic, so a proper gradient is formed; hence, right-side filling is more common.

FUNCTIONS OF PERICARDIUM

- Therefore, if there is a thick fibrotic pericardium, the pressure is not transmitted and hence blood flows from the SVC to the RA during inspiration, so the JVC rises with inspiration rather than falling, known as Kussmaul's sign.
- Interventricular dependence: Inspiratory augmentation of RV filling with no change in LV filling causes bowling of the septum from the R to L, impairing left-sided output.
- This results in a slight inspiratory dip in SBP known as pulsus normalis, typically measuring <10 mmHg.
- Pulsus paradoxus or pulsus normalis aggregans (>10 mmHg)

Figure 2: Mechanism of pulsus paradoxus

Source: mechanism of pulsus paradoxus - Bing images

- Accommodating the excess blood in the pericardial sac, expansion is lost in pericardial disease, resulting in diastolic dysfunction.
- Transmural filling pressure = intracavity pressure - intrapericardial pressure.

Variation of diastolic pressure:

In the presence of a normal pericardium and empty pericardial sac, the diastolic pressure of the RV and LV vary during the respiratory cycle independent of each other.

Figure 4: Ventricular Diastolic Pressure

Source: Pericardial Dse Cath Lab (slideshare.net)

ACUTE PERICARDITIS

Case of 30 yr male, ECG shows ST elevation,

Blood urea-202 mg\dl, Sr, Creat-10.5 mg\dl

(Other investigations required echocardiography to check for minimal effusion and rule out tamponade).

- Another typical example of pericarditis with:
- Widespread ST elevation PR depression.
- Reciprocal ST depression and PR elevation in V1 and aVR.

CHRONIC CONSTRICTIVE PERICARDITIS

It is an end stage of an inflammatory process involving the pericardium where there is abnormally thickened, adherent, inflamed, or calcific pericardium (symmetrical involvement) limiting diastolic filling of the heart (rock-like pericardium).

Cause:

- Relapsing viral > TB
- Post CABG\AVR\Radiation
- Post-histoplasmosis
- CTD(IGg4)
- Malignancy

Functions of the pericardium:

- Transmission
- Expansion
- Interventricular dependence
- Concordance (LV and RV pressure in systole) and discordance (LV and RV pressure in diastole)

Trans myocardial filling pressure=intracavitary pressure-intrapericardial pressure.

If intrapericardial pressure increases, filling decreases (diastolic dysfunction)

Transmission: fall in intrathoracic pressure transmitted to the cardiac chambers.

Rock-like pericardium: no transmission of pressures.

During inspiration, the SVC cannot empty properly into the RA, resulting in elevated JVP (Kussmaul's sign), which is also seen in restrictive cardiomyopathy and tricuspid stenosis.

Systole is normal.

Intrapericardial pressure continues to increase, and eventually, elevation and equalization of diastolic pressure occurs in the post 1/3rd part of diastole (pericardium and the 4 chambers of hearts will have the same pressure).

Phase	JVP	Constrictive pericarditis
Atrial contraction	'a' wave	NORMAL
Atrial relaxation	'x' descent	NORMAL
Atrial filling	'v' wave	NORMAL
Atrial Emptying	'y' descent	SHARP PROMINENT Y DESCENT

Atrial filling occurs during systole

In diastole, ventricular filling occurs only in the 1st 1/3rd part

Later, no filling occurs.

Ventricular pressure plot:

1. Early dip in diastolic pressure due to isovolumetric relaxation.
2. Rapid filling of the 1st 1/3rd diastole increases the pressure.
3. Pericardial knock (early diastolic)
4. Plateau phase due to rigid and thickened pericardium abruptly halting filling.

FINDINGS

Diastolic dysfunction ---> RAP increases ---> increased venous pressure (ascites, edema, JVP, hepatomegaly)

The patient presented with features of right heart failure.
 Chronically ill patient with muscle wasting and cachexia (as in cirrhosis of liver)
 Ascites is the first feature to develop (ascitic precox)
 MRI (diagnostic): rigid, thickened, calcified pericardium,
 Doppler: Exaggerated tricuspid valve inflow velocity (inspiration) and mitral valve inflow velocity (expiration).

EPIDEMIOLOGY

ADULTS

The clinical representation of acute myocarditis in adults is variable, ranging from subclinical to chronic heart failure. If the infection cause is viral, this includes fever, rashes, fatigue, GI and respiratory symptoms. Patients may feel fatigue, palpitations, less working out tolerance or syncope. Chest pain can mimic typical angina and show changes in ECG, such as ST-segment elevation. There is also a chance of CAV occurring in patients with myocarditis.

However, in the case of pericarditis, chest pain is mostly seen. Patients with sudden onset typically present with severe heart failure symptoms, leading to cardiogenic shock.

CHILDREN

Clinical representation in children changes according to age. Symptoms such as anxiousness, fever, reduced appetite, tachypnea and cyanosis can be seen in infants. Children above age 2 also have symptoms such as chest pain, abdominal pain, and edema. Here, severity depends on the age of the children, that is, if age is less, there is a greater chance of being affected by chronic diseases. Children need more support at the early stage of the disease.

Acute pericarditis is one of the most common forms of pericardial disease. This can cause chest pain. This is associated with trauma in uremic patients and malignant diseases. It is more common in men. [1] People with pericarditis can also suffer from chest pain, which usually worsens when taking a deep breath.

RISK FACTORS

Risk factors for myocarditis are not entirely known. Some factors, such as malnutrition, pregnancy, and sex hormones, have been shown. We should also be careful about selenium deficiency, vitamin E deficiency, and other increases in viral virulence. Viral factors, including genome phenotypes, have been shown. Pericarditis occurs in people of all ages. However, primarily men aged 20 to 50 are at higher risk than others. This disease can affect us again even if we get treated this once. This happens to approximately 15% to 30% of people who had this condition before. Sometimes a small number of people may develop chronic pericarditis due to this.

Source: Endocarditis, myocarditis, and pericarditis (Systemic infection) (Medical Microbiology and Infection) (what-when-how.com)

ETIOLOGY

INFECTIOUS

Infectious and noninfectious myocarditis. The most common cause is viral infections.

- **VIRUS:** The viruses frequently identified are adenovirus and enterovirus, including coxsackie virus. Recently, EMB samples were used to detect viral genomes such as parvovirus B-19 and human herpesvirus-6. Some studies have found that they can be a chance of hepatitis C virus. Other myocarditis-associated viruses include cytomegalovirus, herpes simplex virus, and Epstein–Barr virus. [2]

- **BACTERIA:** Bacteria that cause notorious myocarditis can include Salmonella and Shigella. Streptococci, clostridium, tuberculosis, legionellae.

- **PARASITES:** trichinosis, schistosomiasis.

- **PROTOZOA:** Trypanosoma curisi, toxoplasmosis gondii.

- **SPIROCHETES:** borrelia burgdorferi. [5]

NON-INFECTIOUS CAUSES: This includes many causes, such as eosinophilic myocarditis, collagen vascular disease (systemic lupus erythematosus, polymyositis,

Dermatomyositis, cardiotoxic drugs, systemic diseases such as sarcoidosis, inflammatory bowel disease, giant cell arteritis, acute rheumatic fever, venoms and chemicals such as hydrocarbons, and cellular rejection after a cardiac transplant.

Dressler syndrome, also called “late post myocardial syndrome” here pericarditis, occurs after acute coronary syndrome with a delayed inflammatory response. [3]

MAJOR CAUSE OF PERICARDIAL DISEASE CAN BE:

1. **INFECTIONS:** viral, tubercular

2. **NEOPLASM:** metastatic – lung of breast cancer, Hodgkin disease, leukemia, melanoma
 Primary- teratoma, fibroma, angioma
 Paraneoplastic

3. **CARDIAC:** Early infarction pericarditis

4. **AUTOIMMUNE:**

5. **DRUGS**

6. **METABOLIC**

7. **TRAUMA**

8. RADIATION

CAUSES FOR PERICARDITIS CAN ALSO BE:

- Postviral pericarditis (most common), coxsackievirus infection, HIV, TB
- Post MI. (aspirin needs to be increased)
- Uremia
- Post-traumatic
- Drugs such as procainamide\hydralazine\minoxidil
- Tumors such as mesotheliomas, small cell lung ca
- Autoimmune conditions SLE, Sjogren’s, LgG4.

Myocardial ischemia	Or infarction	
Findings	Infarction	Pericarditis
Chest pain		
Character	Pressure-like heavy, squeezing	Sharp, stabbing, occasionally dull Worsened with inspiration
Change with respiration	NO	Worsened with inspiration
Change with position	NO	Worse when supine improved when sitting up if leaning forward
Duration	Minutes (ischemia)	Hours to days

PERICARDIAL FRICTION RUB

- Inflammation of the pericardial sac with or without fluid.
- Very high pitched
- Leathery
- Scratchy in nature
- Seem close to the scar
- Auscultated best with the patient learning forward or knee- chest position.
- Holding their breath after forced expiration.

Figure 6: pericarditis ECG stages

Source: pericarditis ecg stages - Bing images

At 4 to 6 weeks:

Figure 7: Electrical alternans: Acute pericarditis progressed to cardiac tamponade. Spodick sign: Significant TP segment depression.

Figure 8: Spodick sign

Source: Spodick Sign - Bing images

Figure 10: Acute pericarditis with significant effusion: water bottle configuration

Source: acute pericarditis with significant effusion - Bing images

Figure 9 Acute pericarditis with effusion.

Source: acute pericardial with significant effusion - Bing images

PATHOLOGY

Myocarditis is an inflammatory cardiomyopathy. This process is initiated after the entry of the virus into myocardial cells. This activates the innate immune response and thus the adaptive immune response over the next week. Pathogenesis was divided into 3 phases. It is classified based on clinical observations and animal model data.

ACUTE INFECTIOUS PHASE

Here, the first phase lasts from 1 to 7 days, including acute cardiac cell damage, host protein exposure and innate immune activation.

Myocardial injury can vary on the basis of the causative agent: adenovirus and enterovirus.

Through the transmembrane, the cytolitic virus enters myocytes and causes severe cytopathic effects by various processes, including viral protease 2A, which mediates the host protein dystrophin [5].

Finally, for other viruses, including influenza virus, the direct cause of myocarditis here is the self-reactive T-cell response by molecular mimicry between viral and cardiac antigens. [3]

The innate immune system eradicates viral infection, but a more persistent response causes tissue damage.

SUBACUTE IMMUNE PHASE

The second phase lasts from 1-4 weeks. Disease is shown by an adaptive T-cell-mediated immune response. The effects of both CD4+ and CD8 cells have been determined, and there are only limited data available for the pathogen genesis of B cells in viral myocarditis. [3]

RECOVERY PHASE

Eviction pathogens from the myocardium usually obtain cardiac function without residual injury. However, the persistent myocardial infection breakdown of T-cell tolerance leads to chronic inflammation.

Figure 10. Three-phase model for the pathogenesis of myocarditis.

Photo courtesy: Frontiers | Viral Myocarditis: Classification, Diagnosis, and Clinical Implications (frontiersin.org)

CLASSIFICATION

1] POSSIBLE SUBCLINICAL ACUTE MYOCARDITIS: Subclinical myocarditis if there are no symptoms then there can be an increase in troponin or ECG after an acute viral illness, adverse drug reaction.

2] PROBABLE ACURE MYOCARDITIS: diagnosis is done by checking some clinical syndromes such as:

- 1) Chest pain
- 2) Acute heart failure
- 3) Presyncope or syncope
- 4) Myopericarditis

3] DEFINITE MYOCARDITIS: This diagnosis is done by checking the histological analysis of heart tissue.

4] MYOCARDITIS RESEMBLING HEART ATTACK: Myocarditis can present with chest pain because of inflammation of the blood vessel supplying the heart.

5] MYOCARDITIS RESEMBLING ACUTE AND CHRONIC HEART FAILURE:

Here, there may be shortness of breath and fatigue. These patients generally have enlarged heart symptoms with b2 weeks to a few months after infection. [6-12]

DIAGNOSIS: UREMIC PERICARDITIS

Sharp chest pain, stabbing, and pleuritic pain were relieved by sitting up and leaning forward.

On auscultation pericardial friction rub,

ECG shows global ST elevation followed by diffusion.

Frequent PR segment depression

No reciprocal inversion

Figure 11: Widespread concave ST segment elevation.

Source: Acute Pericarditis: Diagnosis and Management | AAFP

TREATMENT

There are minimal data for the treatment of myopericarditis. Nonsteroidal anti-inflammatory drugs can be given if there is more pericarditis illness in left ventricular function. However, in the case of myocardial function, we suggest NSAIDs, which worsen myocardial function. Therefore, the minimum dose is used for relief, which is symptomatic. Therefore, if the patient has signs and symptoms of heart failure with the chance of myocardial involvement, standard heart failure therapy with the help of beta blockers, angiotensin-converting enzymes, and diuretics should be administered. Colchicine is used daily in patients with pericarditis. However, this has no role in myocarditis.[13]

Other treatments include the following:

- Antibiotics
- Antiviral interferon A
- Oral therapy with ACE inhibitors
- Digoxin
- Oxygen therapy
- Corticosteroids and immunosuppressants
- Heart transplant

Pericardectomy/pericardial resection is the definitive treatment and should be performed as early as possible.

Figure 12: Proper atrial waveform demonstrating prominent y descent and suitable ventricular waveform showing diastolic dip and plateau tracing, also called the square root sign.

Source: right atrium waveform demonstrating prominent y descent - Bing images

Pulsus paradoxus: seen in 1\3rd patients with pericarditis. Poor LVC filling due to low pulmonary venous pressure and normal LV pressure.

Septal blood flow is high, and thus, ventricular interdependence

Reduced apex, which retracts in systole followed by rebound (Broadbent's sign)

Normal-sized heart.

Low voltage QRS complexes and diffuse flattening of T waves.

Pericardial calcifications are nonspecific. An obliterated pericardial cavity cannot transmit the changes in intrathoracic pressure in respiration to cardiac chambers.

Exaggerated ventricular interdependence seen in 1\3rd.

For diagnosis, we can check the following:

ECG

CHEST X-RAY

Myocardial inflammatory and injury markers such as ESR, CRP, and troponins.

PROPHYLAXIS

There is no prevention of myocarditis. However, staying distant from people with flu symptoms and other respiratory infections might help.

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